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DETECTION AND MONITORING OF ADVERSE DRUG REACTIONS DUE TO ANTIPSYCHOTICS IN A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Adverse drug reactions are well known to occur with any class of drugs when used in normal doses for the management of diseases and prophylaxis. Antipsychotic drugs are no exception to this. The main aim of this study was to detect and monitor adverse drug reactions in inpatients of Psychiatry department in a tertiary care hospital. **Methodology:** It is a prospective observational study carried out for a period of six months, after getting approval from human ethical committee among the inpatients of the department of psychiatry, Shri Mahant Indresh Hospital, Dehradun. **Result:** Total 133 patients were screened for this study, out of which 37 patients were detected with ADR. Incidence of ADRs was higher in females (51.3%) than in males (48.6%). The age group mostly affected was between 20-39 years of age. The most commonly reported ADR observed was dizziness among 15(40.54%) patients followed by headache among 6(16.21%) patients, insomnia among 5(13.51%) patients, Akathisia among 5(13.51%) patients, chest pain among 1(2.70%) and sedation among 1(2.70%) patients. The most commonly antipsychotic drug responsible for the cause of ADR was Olanzapine (32.43%) followed by Haloperidol (21.62%), Clozapine (13.51%), Quetiapine (10.81%), Risperidone (8.10%), Trifluoperazine (5.40), Flupenthixol (2.70%), Aripiprazole (2.70%) and Amisulpride (2.70%). Majority of ADRs were of type A (67.56%) according to WHO classification. Majority of ADRs were assessed as probable (91.90%) according to "Naranjo Causality Scale". Majority of ADRs were assessed as Moderate (59.45%) and rest were Mild (40.54%) according to modified Hartwig-Seigel severity assessment scale. The outcome of ADRs reported was 29(78.38%) cases recovered while 8(21.62%) cases were reported to be recovering and no fatal outcome was observed. **Conclusion:** The study shows that both typical as well as atypical Antipsychotic drugs can cause ADRs. So there is need to implement the guidelines for Antipsychotic drug use in hospital setting and ADR management through therapeutic interventions would be beneficial in the better patient outcome.

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INTRODUCTION

According to WHO, adverse drug reaction is defined as “Any response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function”¹. Antipsychotic drugs are chemically diverse but possess the common property of alleviating the symptoms of both functional and organic psychosis². These drugs can be of great benefit in a range of psychiatric disorders including bipolar affective disorders and schizophrenia and their use is increasing day by day, but all are capable of causing a wide range of potential adverse reactions that can lead to non-compliance, can impair quality of life, cause stigma, cause physical morbidity leading to discontinuation of medication and in extreme cases be fatal³. Antipsychotic drugs are plentiful in numbers and their use is increasing day by day, which are capable of causing numbers of ADRs^{4, 5}, some of which may be fatal⁶. ADRs associated with antipsychotic drugs can lead to non-compliance and or discontinuation of therapy⁷. Pharmacovigilance in psychiatry units can play a vital role in detecting ADRs and alerting physicians to the possibility, circumstances and consequences of such events, thereby protecting the user population from avoidable harm.

In India, Pharmacovigilance activities are still in nascent stages and there are only few reports available on the profile of antipsychotic drugs. This leads us to evaluate the ADR profile of Antipsychotic drugs used in psychiatry department of tertiary care hospital (SMIH), Dehradun.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design:

It is prospective observation study carried out for a period of six months after getting approval from human ethical committee.

Study Population:

Depends on the number of patients reporting the adverse drug events during the study period.

Place of study:

Inpatients of psychiatry department of Shri Mahant Indresh Hospital, Dehradun.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. The subjects admitted to psychiatric department in hospital.
2. Admitted subjects of either sex of any age group who develop an ADR.

Exclusion criteria:

1. The Subjects admitted due to overdose (either accidental or Intentional) & drug abuse.
 2. Drug Administration error.
 3. Subjects admitted in ICU.
 4. Subjects not willing to participate in the study.
- A prior consent was taken from the attendants.

Recording of Data:

All the details were collected in a suitable designed document for suspected drug reaction filled in ADR form. All subjects were reviewed on the daily basis. The detailed history was taken and clinical examination of all subjects will be done. History including pre-existing medical condition like allergy, pregnancy, smoking and alcohol used or any organ dysfunction was noted. If any suspected ADR is detected, all the detail regarding suspected drug viz type of drug, dose of drug, date of starting the drug, duration of drug, and adverse drug reaction viz types of reaction, severity of reactions will be noted. Under suspected medicine, name of drug, brand of manufacturer, generic names of manufacturer as well as reason of prescribing suspected drug were also assessed. The information of de-challenge and re-challenge, concomitant medical treatment record, the relevant laboratory biochemical abnormality was also recorded.

Simple statistical methods were used to determine:-

1. All different adverse drug reactions caused by antipsychotics.
2. Most commonly antipsychotic drug associated with adverse drug reactions.
3. Causality of adverse drug reactions was assessed as per Naranjo causality assessment scale⁸.
4. Severity of adverse drug reactions was assessed by “modified Hartwig-Seigel scale¹”.

RESULTS:-

Screening of subjects:-

Total 133 patients were screened for this study, out of which 37 patients develop ADRs. The details about the detected ADRs are summarized as following:

Details of adverse drug reactions reported in the psychiatric department.

During the study period of majority of ADR detected were in females in comparison to males and the age duration mostly affected between 20 to 39 years of age.

Table 1: Age wise distribution of ADRs in psychiatric department.

Age	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
11-19	2 (5.40%)	2 (5.40%)	4 (10.8)
20-39	11 (29.72%)	8 (21.62%)	19 (51.3)
40-59	4 (10.81%)	6 (16.21%)	10 (26.0)
≥60	1 (2.70%)	3 (8.10%)	4 (10.8)
Total	18 (48.6%)	19 (51.3%)	37 (100%)

The most commonly antipsychotic drug that causes the ADR was Olanzapine (32.43%) followed by Haloperidol (21.62%), Clozapine (13.51%), Quetiapine (10.81%), Risperidone (8.10%), Trifluoperazine (5.40), Flupenthixol (2.70%), Aripiprazole (2.70%) and Amisulpride (2.70%).

Table 2: Therapeutic class of antipsychotics implicated to cause ADR in Psychiatric department.

Name of drug	Class of drug	No. of ADRs	% of ADR in various classes
Olanzapine	Atypical antipsychotic	12	32.43%
Haloperidol	Typical antipsychotic	8	21.62%
Clozapine	Atypical antipsychotic	5	13.51%
Quetiapine	Atypical antipsychotic	4	10.81%
Risperidone	Atypical antipsychotic	3	8.10%
Trifluoperazine	Typical antipsychotic	2	5.40%
Flupenthixol	Typical antipsychotic	1	2.70%
Aripiprazole	Atypical antipsychotic	1	2.70%
Amisulpride	Atypical antipsychotic	1	2.70%

The most commonly reported ADR observed in the present study was dizziness among 15(40.54%) subjects, followed by headache among 6(16.21%), insomnia among 5(13.51%), Akathisia among 5(13.51%), chest pain among 1(2.70%) and sedation among 1(2.70%).

Table 3: Adverse reactions reported by Antipsychotic drugs in psychiatric department.

Type of Reactions	No. of ADRs	%
Dizziness	19	51.35
Headache	6	16.21
Insomnia	5	13.51
Akathisia	5	13.51
Chest pain	1	2.70
Sedation	1	2.70

During the study out of 37 (78.37%) subjects 29(78.38) cases recovered that suffered from ADR, while 8(21.62%) cases were reported to be recovering and there was no fatal outcome observed.

Table 4: Outcome of ADR reported due to Antipsychotic drugs.

Parameters	No. of ADRs	Percentage %
Fatal	0	0
Recovering	8	21.62
Recovered	29	78.38
Unknown	0	0
Others	0	0

Fig 4: Outcome of ADRs Reported Due to Antipsychotic Drugs

According to Naranjo scale, the causality assessment of suspected ADRs, it was found that 3(8.10%) cases were definite and 34(91.90%) cases were probable.

Table 5: causality assessment according to Naranjo Scale of ADRs due to Antipsychotic drugs.

Causality assessment	No. of ADRs	Percentage (%)
Definite	3	8.10%
Probable	34	91.90%
Possible	0	0
Unlikely	0	0

On assessment the severity level by modified Hartwig-Seigel scale, 15(40.54%) cases were mild and 22(59.45%) cases were moderate.

Table 6: Level of severity by modified Hartwig-Seigel scale of ADRs due to Antipsychotic drugs.

Level of Severity	No. of ADRs	Percentage (%)
Mild	15	40.54
Moderate	22	59.45
Severe	0	0

DISCUSSION

As per the NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICES regarding the use of antipsychotics as first line agents, it is said that first and second generation antipsychotics are equally efficacious but when no consensus is reached between their to start the second generation ones. Various studies have seen that the second generation antipsychotics were having fewer adverse effects and though both groups were equally efficacious⁹. Thus it is seen that use of second generation antipsychotics are more than first generation antipsychotics.

Some important aspects regarding this study:

- ✓ This prospective study highlights the incidence and pattern of ADRs of Antipsychotics in a tertiary care hospital of the country.
- ✓ In our study we found incidence of ADRs was 51.3% in females and 48.6% in males. Olanzapine was the frequently used drug having highest number of ADRs (32.43%) and dizziness was the commonest ADR. A similar study was done in a tertiary care hospital of Assam in 2014, reported incidence of ADRs was 66.67% in males and 33.33% in females. Olanzapine was the commonest drug causing ADRs (12.8%) and Tremor was the commonest ADR (36.36%)¹⁰.
- ✓ Regarding causality assessment, our study has no “certain” cases since ADRs reported were mild to moderate. In cases where dechallenge was done, rechallenge in some cases was attempted with the offending drug. This is in contrast to a Brazilian study where 23 cases were found to “definite” after rechallenge was attempted¹¹.
- ✓ Using “Naranjo Causality Assessment Scale”⁷, most ADRs were assessed as probable in 91.90% cases and 8.10% cases were assessed as definite. 78.38% of cases were fully recovered and 21.62% cases were recovering. This study suggests that better management is required for drug therapy.
- ✓ Severity assessment was done according to modified Hartwig-Seigel scale criteria. Mild reactions 40.54% did not require any change in prescribed and increase the hospital stay. Moderate reactions 59.45% require immediate stop for causative drug therapy and substitution with alternative drug and also treatment to the reaction.
- ✓ The result of this study has pointed that some of the factors like advancing age, irrational drug combination, and polypharmacy can cause increase in adverse events.

CONCLUSION

Nowadays antipsychotics are frequently used drugs and their ADRs are plentiful, which leads to non-compliance, behavioral changes and discontinuation of therapy. Our study provides a representative idea of prescribing pattern changes and ADRs likely to be occurred in a tertiary care hospital of India. A constant Pharmacovigilance in detecting and subsequent dose adjustments can make the antipsychotic drug therapy safer, more effective and have more patient compliance.

To conclude, an antipsychotic drug database built upon the basis of such studies conducted across multiple centers, through active collaboration of psychiatrists and pharmacologists can be a high yielding long term goal in Indian context.

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